

THE INFLUENCE OF ONLINE LEARNING IN ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF SULU NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10998881>

ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals with the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School. It also deals with the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of gender, age, and grade level, the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School. It also deals with the significant difference in the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School when data are grouped according to demographic profile in terms of gender, age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment. The study was conducted at Sulu National High School and the respondents of the study are the secondary high school students of Sulu National High School. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents of the study. The research instrument is composed of two parts. Part I is about the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their gender, age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment Part II is composed of 20 statements on the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary high school students of Sulu National High School. There are 5 levels to choose from which ranges from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree". It was found that the secondary school students of Sulu National High School are in their early teens for their present grade level, almost equal number were taken from each grade level, and the parents are not very educated. The respondents agree on the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among them. There is no significant difference in the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School in terms of demographic profile.

Keywords: *Online Learning, English Language Learning, SNHS, Descriptive Research.*

INTRODUCTION

The process of delivering instruction and educational materials using the internet is called online learning, sometimes referred to as distant learning or eLearning. Students can complete their coursework and earn degrees without having to visit campuses thanks to it. Self-paced learning programs, video conferencing, and web-based classes are just a few of the numerous shapes that online learning can take. Because of its ease and adaptability, students are using this type of training more and more.

Facebook and other social media sites should be used in teaching and learning activities as a platform for students' autonomous study, claims Kitchakarn (2016). They would be able to express their ideas, opinions, remarks, and sentiments while also finishing tasks and improving their writing and grammar skills. Wang, Cheng, Chen, Mercer, and Kirschner (2017) use concept mapping in the classroom as a tool for group collaboration and participation. Such concepts are derived from a variety of computer and web-based tools utilized in the online environment.

Hee-jung Jung conducted a study in 2015 titled "Fostering an English Teaching Environment: Factors Influencing English as a Foreign Language Teachers' Adoption of Mobile Learning". The importance of mobile technology in English language education has increased and been brought to light. Regrettably, research on the attitudes and actions of EFL instructors towards mobile technology has not given enough attention to descriptive features of it, leading to misconceptions about what it requires. Additionally, from the viewpoint of English language learners, a number of earlier research have looked at various facets of electronic learning (e-learning) and technological advancements in mobile learning (m-learning). Consequently, this study provided a research approach that uses Fred Davis's Technology Acceptance methodology (TAM) as the research framework to empirically evaluate the m-learning acceptance behaviors of EFL teachers. This research model includes the following external aspects that influence people's perceptions of the usefulness of TAM: instantaneous connectivity, compatibility, interaction, content enrichment, and computer self-efficacy. The data of 189 EFL teachers was subjected to structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis in order to determine the causal linkages between external variables and TAM variables. The outcomes offer proof that the tested theories are correct. Future research on mobile learning may need to veer in a new route due to the implications of the findings.

Shahid, C., Gurmani, M. T., Rehman, S. U, & Saif, L. (2023) "The Role of Technology in English Language Learning in Online Classes at Tertiary Level". The investigation of the link is the study's main goal between the elements of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and internet using programs to learn languages. Furthermore, the study has looked into the impact of gender and past technology use habits. To obtain data, this study employed a TAM and a quantitative technique to analyze user responses

to the language learning system survey. There are one hundred participants in the study. Students taking online courses in undergraduate English as a second language during the COVID-19 epidemic. The intents, attitudes, and behaviours of students and app usage were discovered to have a strong positive correlation in the study's findings. Furthermore, there is a favorable correlation among the following factors: behavior, perceived use, real use, and seen usability. Gender does not seem to be related to any TAM component, although experience has been demonstrated to positively correlate with TAM components. According to the study, kids can enjoy learning a second language more when technology is included in the classroom.

Min Yang, Pauline Mak, Rui Yuan (2021) "Feedback Experience of Online Learning During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Voices from Pre-service English Language Teachers". Using the concept of help seeking as a guide, this study aims to explore an online feedback experience of a group of MATESOL students regarding their professional learning during the COVID-19 pandemic (Newman, 2008). Analysis of the participant's written reflections from the online courses and interviews with them showed that while online feedback created challenges like limited real-time and extensive feedback, it also offered learning opportunities like the ability to give and receive feedback in diverse groups within a safe environment. Although they occasionally exhibited nonadoptive help seeking, the participants developed adaptive help seeking methods in response to criticism. These strategies included remaining resilient, seeking out alternative methods of accepting criticism, setting up feedback-generating internal meetings with educational resources, and creating a forum for participation and input from close friends and family. In order to promote pre-service teachers' adaptive help-seeking methods in feedback situations as critical and self-regulated learners who may contribute to their professional growth, the study closes with practical recommendations to improve pre-service teachers' online feedback experience.

Research Questions

The research study provided answers to the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of;
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Grade Level; and
 - 1.4 Parent's Educational Attainment?
2. What is the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School?

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School when data are group according to their demographic profile;

3.1 Gender;

3.2 Age;

3.3 Grade Level; and

3.4 Parent's Educational Attainment?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

In order to ascertain how online learning has affected secondary students' in Sulu National High School, this study used a descriptive-survey research approach. The aforementioned design outlined any potential repercussions of putting the remote learning program in place.

This style was utilized to create information on the subject. The goal of the research is to describe and quantify the impact of online learning on English language understanding. They made sense of their uncertainty in their field of study using this design.

Research Locale

This study focused on numerous secondary students in Sulu National High School. This was conducted at the said school during the year 2023-2024. It is one of the most populated school in the Province of Sulu.

Respondents of the Study

Participants in this study are Sulu National High School secondary students. The purpose of the survey is to find out what the respondents think about the influence of online learning on English language understanding. The aforementioned respondents are arranged according to their academic specialization.

Distribution of the target samples among secondary school students.

Patikul District, MBHTE-Sulu Sulu National High School		
Grade level	Section	Frequency
Grade 7	12	25
Grade 8	12	25
Grade 9	11	25
Grade 10	11	25
Total		100

Sampling Design

The purposive sampling procedure was used as the sampling technique. To collect data from the respondents, the researcher employed a sampling approach. This protocol is the suitable method to gather data from the participants. Subsequently, the survey questionnaire is distributed.

The researchers can quickly get the information they require for their respondents by using this sampling technique. All they do is give the survey questions to the chosen respondents.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the collection of the data, the following steps were employed:

1) Permission to conduct the survey was requested from the Dean of the Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College and then from the School Principal of Sulu National High School and then from the Senior High school Coordinator.

2) The researcher launched and administered the questionnaire herself, as well as retrieving it.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the instruments in this study in gathering the data on demographic profile and the extent of the Influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School.

The survey questionnaire was utilized to obtain the data on the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu during the Year 2023-2024. This questionnaire

was adapted and patterned from Choosri Banditvilai (2016) Enhancing Students' Language Skills through Blended Learning.

The research instruments employed in this study were divided into two components. First, part of the questionnaire focused on obtaining the demographic profile of the respondents which includes Gender, Age, Grade level and Parent's Educational Attainment. And, the second part focused on the collection of data on the extent of the Influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School.

Under the extent of the Influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School contained twenty (20) items and will be answered through 5-points likert scales such as 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3=Undecided, 2=Disagree, 1=strongly disagree.

Statistical Treatment of Data

1. For the research problem number one (1), the frequency percentage was used to ascertain the respondents' age, gender, grade level, and parents' educational attainment as well as the socio-demographic profile of Sulu National High School students, MBHTE-Sulu.
2. For the research problem number two (2), the means and standard deviation was utilized to evaluate the influence of online learning in enhancing English language at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu.
3. For the research problem number (3), In order to find significant differences in the degree to which the influence of online learning approach in enhancing English language learning among Secondary school students at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu, research problem number three used the t-test for independent samples for Gender. When data were grouped according to age, Grade level, and Parents educational attainment, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to find significant differences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the socio - demographic profile of the secondary school students of Sulu National High School in terms of 1.1 gender, 1.2 ag, 1.3 grade level, and 1.4 parent's educational attainment?

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. Fifty-eight percent (45%) of the respondents are females and 42% are males. The result implies that the female respondents comprised the majority.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	42	42%
Female	58	58%
TOTAL	100	100%

1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. It showed that 50% of the respondents are between 11 – 15 years old and only 1% are 10 years old and below.

The result implies that half the respondents are in their early teens in terms of gender.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
10 years old and below	1	1%
11 – 15 years old	50	50%
16 – 20 years old	47	47%
21 years old and above	2	2%
TOTAL	100	100%

1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of grade level. It showed that almost equal number of respondents belong to the different grade level.

The result implies that the researcher tried to balance the number of respondents from each grade level.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 7	24	24%
Grade 8	25	25%
Grade 9	25	25%
Grade 10	26	26%
TOTAL	100	100%

1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of parent's educational attainment. It showed that 38% of the parents reached high school level in education while only 6% reached finished either masters or doctorate degree.

The result implies that only a few of the parents were highly educated.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	8	8%
Elementary Level	21	21%
High School Level	38	38%
College Level	27	27%
Masters/Doctorate Degree	6	6%
TOTAL	100	100 %

2. What is the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School?

Table 2 presents the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School.

It showed that the respondents indicated either agree or undecided on the Different statements on the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning. Among those statements they indicated agree are; students who is addicted in e – learning can speak English fluently (mean = 4.360, SD = .560); the students' learning experience is enhanced by this e – learning program (mean = 4.380, SD = .599); this e – learning program develops students' speaking skills (mean = 4.430, SD = .624); and the teacher should use this program to supplement in – class teaching (mean = 4.270, SD = .446). The average mean of 3.889 means that the secondary school students of Sulu National High School agree on the influence of online learning in enhancing English language Learning.

The result simply implies that online learning a positive effect in enhancing English language learning among the secondary school students of Sulu National High School. In a study conducted by Alsulami (2016), the result unequivocally shows that online learning is beneficial for English language learners.

Table 2 Extent of the Influence of Online Learning in Enhancing English Language Learning among Secondary School Students of Sulu National High School

Influence of Online Learning	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. The e-learning lessons help the students understand the subject matter.	4.190	.394	Agree
2. The lessons in the e – learning program are interesting.	4.040	.400	Agree
3. The teacher should use this program to supplement in – class teaching.	4.270	.446	Agree
4. This e – learning program motivates the students to study by themselves.	4.130	.338	Agree
5. The students’ learning experience is enhanced by this e – learning program.	4.380	.599	Agree
6. This e – learning program develops students’ language skills.	4.220	.543	Agree
7. This e – learning program develops students’ listening skills.	4.220	.561	Agree
8. This e – learning program develops students’ speaking skills.	4.430	.624	Agree
9. This e – learning program develops students’ reading skills.	4.340	.623	Agree
10. This e – learning program develop students’ writing skills.	4.250	.592	Agree
11. e – learning can enhance students motivation in learning English.	4.390	.601	Agree
12. Students who is addicted in e – learning can speak English fluently.	4.360	.560	Agree
13. I think I can improve my English speaking skills through online learning.	4.030	.437	Agree
14. I believe learning through online will increase the cost of learning.	3.677	.550	Agree
15. Learning through online will help me to utilize my time productively.	3.670	.684	Agree
16. e – learning cannot build teamwork and collaboration.	2.580	1.224	Undecided
17. e – learning develops students’ confidence in learning English language.	3.920	1.032	Agree
18. The students’ learning experience is distracted by this e – learning program.	2.610	1.421	Undecided
19. I believe e – learning will not provide any advantages for me.	2.510	1.059	Undecided
20. I think I can learn well through online learning program.	3.570	.607	Agree
AVERAGE	3.889		AGREE

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50 – 4.49	Agree
3	2.50 – 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

Is there a significant difference in the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School when data are grouped according to gender, age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment?

The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.330 is greater than the p – value of .05, 2- tailed tests. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the influence of online learning Sulu in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School when data are grouped according to their gender.

The result implies that regardless of gender, online learning has the same influence in enhancing English language learning among the secondary school students of Sulu National High School.

In a study by Gurmani, Rehman, and Saif (2023), the result showed that gender does not seem to be connected to Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) components.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Influence of Online Learning in Enhancing English Language Learning among Secondary School Students of Sulu National High School in terms of Gender

Variables		Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning	Male	4.790	.580	0.440	24.580	.330	Not Significant
	Female	4.350	.720				

Significant at .05 level

In Table 3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment.

The sig. value of 0.133 for age is greater than the p - value of .05, the sig. value of 0.198 for grade level is greater than the p-value at .05, and the sig. value of 0.224 for parent's Educational attainment is also greater than the p - value of .05. It could only mean that the null hypothesis is accepted in terms of age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School District when data are grouped according to their age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment.

The result implies that the different demographic profiles of the secondary school students of Sulu National High School cannot predict the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning.

The "community of inquiry" Model, developed by Anderson, Rourke, Garrison, and Archer (2001) for online learning environments, is predicated on the notion of three distinct "presences" (cognitive, social, and teaching).

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Influence of Online Learning in Enhancing English Language Learning among Secondary School Students of Sulu National High School in terms of Age, Grade Level, and Parent's Educational Attainment

		Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.	Interpretation
AGE							
Groups	Between	1.644	3	.548	1.912	.133	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.516	96	.287			
	Total		99				
Grade Level							
Groups	Between	.962	3	.321	2.071	.198	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.878	96	.155			
	Total	15.840	99				
Parent's Educational Attainment							
Groups	Between	.884	4	.221	1.447	.224	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.506	95	.153			
	Total	15.390	99				

Significant at .05 level

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

The secondary school students of Sulu National High School were mostly females, in their early teens, and with parents who are not very educated.

It only showed that online learning significantly enhanced English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School.

The absence of difference in the extent of the influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among secondary school students of Sulu National High School when data are grouped according to gender, age, grade level, and parent's educational attainment only proves that demographic profiles of the students cannot determine the exact influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Further study on the extent of influence of online learning in enhancing English language learning among students must be conducted to really prove if it does influence them or not.
2. Future researchers on the same topic should add variables like availability, strength of internet signal and other variables not covered by this study.
3. Teachers should constantly remind learners to balance their online learning and outdoor activities to keep themselves healthy physically and mentally.
4. Teachers using online teaching should give their best in teaching the learners and constantly remind learners to balance between indoor and outdoor activities.
5. Parents should provide continuous support on their children's online learning activities.
6. School administration should try their best to provide online access to the learners by connecting to any available internet services available in their area.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her sincere gratitude and appreciation to everyone who helped her along the way and provide support.

She expresses her gratitude to the All-Powerful Allah (SWT) for guiding her during the entire thesis writing process.

She is deeply grateful to our very own SUC President II PROF. CHARISMA S. UTUTALUM, CESE, Sulu State College President for granting her permission to study in this institution.

She is very grateful to the members of the thesis committee for their valuable suggestions in accomplishing this work. These are: ASSO.PROF, AURIZIA D. SIRAJI, Adviser and a faculty of School of Education, for her guidance and encouragement

throughout this study; ASSO.PROF, MASNONA S. ASIRI, DPA, Dean of Graduate Studies and ASSO.PROF, NELSON U. JULHAMID, Ph.D, Vice President for Academic Affairs, for their insightful comments and suggestions for the improving of this study.

She would like to extend her warmest gratitude to the Principal of Sulu National High School, MR. DARWIN PANGAMBAYAN, for allowing her to conduct her study in his school as well as to the Junior High School Students for sharing their time in responding to the questionnaire provided.

She would like to dedicate this study to the people who have meant and continue to mean so much. To my precious gift, my little princess Fatima Ayezhra Edris Hadjali, who was born right after my title proposal. She's with me throughout my thesis journey, and she's my inspiration despite the difficulties along the way. To my responsible husband who push me to continue my thesis writing, thank you for your unwavering support be it financially and morally. Your guidance helps me boosted my confidence to pursue my study. You're one of the rarest man I know. To my mother and father, siblings and my 3 grandmas, thank you for believing in my capabilities since day one. Thank you for providing me a great sense of enthusiasm and perseverance in pursuing this study. To my mother-in-law, father-in-law, sister-in-law, thank you for the motivational words that made me believe in myself once again. You raise a great son that's why I have a great husband now. To my friends who were there when I need their help related to my study, thank you! You're all appreciated. And lastly to my Titi/Yaya, who passed away days after I gave birth, I dedicate this study to you. Thank you for raising me, thank you for everything, I can't express my heartfelt gratitude to you personally because you are no longer here, but I will treasure the memories we had. I will forever long your presence and warm smile. Sorry if didn't fulfill my promise before you gone, I thought you were there to celebrate my win when it finally happen, but you left me too early. Even you are no longer in this world, your memories continue to regulate my life forever. I love you and I miss you everyday.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declare that the consent was obtained from the respondents. In addition, the researcher assure that the data obtained from the respondents are kept confidentially. The researchers also tried to provide a friendly and safe space for the participants so they could discuss candidly about their experiences.

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